

IMPORTANCE OF 3D STRESS FIELD IN THE FAILURE OF PIN LOADED JOINT

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ABSTRACT

The three-dimensional characteristic of the failure mode of pin-loaded joint is examined from an experimental and a numerical point of view. Experimental tests are performed for specimens of different lay-up and geometric properties. Special devices assure lateral constraint, applied at different levels. The results obtained in experimental tests are compared with those obtained by a numerical approach, which takes into account accurately the interlaminar stress components, without excessive computing cost. From the numerical results it emerged that failure can be attributed, in absence of lateral constraint, to the interlaminar normal stress σ_z . This result can justify the presence of splitting between layers present in the specimens after the experimental tests.

INTRODUCTION

The prediction of the strength and the failure mode of pin-loaded joint is a paramount problem for the design of aerospace composite structures.

Many authors (ref. 3,4,8,9) developed their studies with the fundamental hypothesis of a bidimensional stress field, neglecting the three-dimensional character of the phenomenon, due to the effect of a lateral constraint. Even if this fact can be reasonable, since a correct joint assembly generally involves the good efficiency of a lateral constraint (bolts or rivets heads, nuts, washers, etc.), however it is not right to leave out of consideration the possibility of a drop of such efficiency in the operating life of the joint. In some works Matthews et al. (ref. 5,6,7) have shown as the failure load and mode depend on whether the load is applied via a pin or a bolt, observing that the failure of a mechanical joint is clearly a three-dimensional phenomenon. Matthews, Wong and Chryssafitis have proposed a numerical approach in order to determine stress field behaviour around the hole, namely as far as interlaminar components are concerned (ref. 7). Such attempts are not fully satisfying because the adopted theoretical approach is not suitable to the features of the problem and requires excessive computational efforts.

Purpose of this paper is to determine the importance of a 3-D stress field, considering the interlaminar stresses who occur if this lateral constraint is inefficient. The present study has been performed by an "ad hoc" finite element computer program and a set of experimental tests of several carbon-epoxy specimens of different geometry.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMS AND RESULTS

The experimental tests have been performed at the laboratories of the Aerospace Department in Rome on carbon-epoxy specimens, supplied by a specialized aeronautical industry.

The unidirectional prepreg utilized has been the fiberite HY-E1034C, with the nominal fiber volume fraction of 60%: its most significant mechanical properties are described in Table 1. The laminates have been cured according to manufacturer's specifications.

The experimental program has included a set of tension tests of pin-loaded hole specimens to determine strength and failure mode with or without a lateral constraint.

The basic specimens configuration and geometry for tension testing are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 2. All tests have been carried out with a RM SCHENK- TREBEL 100 KN at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min; such testing machine is provided of a recorder PHILIPS PM 8032, which has permitted to obtain the plots F-S (F=load, S=displacement).

A special loading device has been adopted, in order to assure correct loading conditions: lateral

constraint could be available to determine its influence as the only consequence of the assembly, depending of the faces shape of two central plates (Fig.2). In fact the groove is such to locate the specimen without any interference; if the two central plates are turned of 180°, there is a contact between their surfaces with those of the specimens.

Typical plots obtained for different configuration of lateral constraints are reported in Fig.3.

In any case a drop of load is observed and its value increases with the efficiency of lateral constraint. When the lateral constraint is absent, the drop occurs at low value of the applied force and corresponds to the failure of the specimen (Fig.3a).

When the lateral constraint is at the start of the test, completely efficient, the drop occurs at higher value of the applied force (Fig.3c).

If the lateral constraint is not completely efficient from the beginning of the test, the drop occurs (Fig.3b) at intermediate levels of the above said values of the applied force and the failure grows up until the lateral constraint becomes efficient. From this moment the drop of load is stopped and the specimen is able to undergo to higher load level.

This kind of behaviour suggests that the absence of the lateral constraint exalts the importance of the interlaminar components of stress field. This suggestion is confirmed by the inspection of the specimen in which splitting between layers is present. In these cases the mode of failure is indicated as "Delamination".

The tests results obtained in both conditions (strenght and failure modes with and without lateral constraint) are reported in Table 3; each failure load is the mean of five values.

The specimens have been considered broken in agreement of the first great drop of load.

From the tests analysis it has been observed:

- a) the presence of delamination in absence of lateral constraint;
- b) a strenght reduction of about 40% for $[(0/90)_6]_s$, assuming 100% the failure load with the constraint;
- c) a strenght reduction of about 50% for $(0^\circ \pm 45^\circ / 90^\circ)_s$ specimens.

These results confirm a general trend of increasing strength with an increasing applied lateral pressure (ref. 5,6,7) and suggest to improve the knowledge of interlaminar stress field in order to analyze the kind of failure which can occur in presence or not of the lateral constraint.

In order to get a better understanding of the phenomenon observed in experimental tests, an accurate numerical stress analysis has been performed.

THEORETICAL APPROACH AND RESULTS

A finite element model has been developed (ref.1,2) which takes into account the 3-D character of the problem, assuming for the displacement field:

$$u(x,y,z) = \sum_{m=0}^M z^m u_m(x,y) \quad v(x,y,z) = \sum_{n=0}^N z^n v_n(x,y) \quad w(x,y,z) = \sum_{k=0}^K z^k w_k(x,y) \quad (1)$$

A triangular 6-nodes plate has been choosed, assuming quadratic shape functions for each unknown u_m, v_n, w_k .

Due to symmetry, only one half of the specimen has been considered (Fig.4.a). Moreover the mesh has been refined in order to get good simulation of the stress field along the coordinates directions (Fig.4.b).

Different geometries have been tested, according to the experimental procedure, in order to study the influence of the ratios a/d and e/d on the stress field.

Along the hole the external load was assigned following the present rule :

$$\vec{T}(\vartheta) = \frac{4P}{\pi dt} \cdot \sin \vartheta \cdot \vec{u}$$

In order to check the validity of the numerical program, the results, obtained assuming $M=N=2$ and $K=1$ in form (1), have been compared with those of De Jong (ref.9) and Chang, Scott and Springer (ref.8), for a hole-loaded isotropic plate obtaining good agreement with those results (Fig.5,6). De Jong and Chang et al. assumed a bi-dimensional theoretical model. The agreement with those models is justified for the 3-D model here presented by the fact that as far as isotropic plates are concerned, no strong 3-D influences emerged for the in-plane stress components.

Then, assuming the experimental failure load as an input of the program, for different geometries, has

been obtained the stress distribution around the hole. To this end it was necessary to produce an higher order model which corresponds to the following assumed values: $M=N=4$ and $K=3$.

For the specimens A and E the normal stress σ_z shows a peak corresponding to $\vartheta=90^\circ$ (Fig.7,8). This value, even if considered alone, is such to justify the failure for delamination, in agreement with experimental results.

For the quasi-isotropic laminate the values of σ_z in $\vartheta=90^\circ$ are higher than those of the $[(0/90)_6]_s$ laminate. Such fact justifies the major tendency to the delamination of the $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminate, in accordance with the experimental tests.

It is important to consider that, due to the theoretical approach fully explained in ref. 1 and 2, the finite element method here proposed can provide good numerical prediction of the stress field without excessive computing cost. The main reason for this is that a limited number of degrees of freedom is taken into account by the finite element model.

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental program has pointed out the presence of delamination as a failure mode in tensile tests for pin loaded joints without lateral pressure; this failure is probably due to the interlaminar stresses. The finite elements analysis, developed in the Aerospace Department of the University of Rome and several times tested, with good accordance with other authors, has shown that the normal stress σ_z around the hole reaches its maximum value for $\vartheta=90^\circ$, at a level which can justify, also neglecting other stresses, the failure of the joint.

For this reasons it is possible to find a fourth failure mode, a delamination one, in addition to net tension, shear out and bearing.

Moreover:

a) the numerical method above described allows to determine the distribution of the stress around the hole, utilizing few elements and taking in account the interlaminar stresses, mostly the normal stress

σ_z ;

b) for a good design of a pin loaded joint it is necessary to be sure of the efficiency of a lateral constraint, in order to avoid a considerable drop of joint strength, depending from the stacking sequence.

c) if any cause will produce a drop of the efficiency of the above mentioned constraint (vibrations or something else), it will be possible to find a delamination around the hole, who can be very dangerous, mostly if fatigue stresses or fatigue-environment effects are present.

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Fig.1 Specimen size.

Fig.2 Loading device.

Product code		HY-E1034C	
Resin system		934	
Reinforcement		UC T-300	
Cure Temperature,°K		450	
Nominal Cure Ply Thickness,mm		0.127	
CURED LAMINATE PROPERTIES	TEST METHOD	TEMP °K	
Flexural strength MPa	M6	297	175
		450	129
Flexural Modulus,GPa	M6	297	118
		450	111
Tensile Strength MPa	M5	297	167
		450	111
Tensile Modulus GPa	M5	297	148
		450	130
Short Beam Shear MPa	M7	297	126
		450	64
Mechanical properties of cured laminate normalized to:			60%

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the unidirectional prepreg.

Type	LAMINATE	a/d	e/d
A	[(0/90) ₂] _s	3.125	3.15
C	[(0/90) ₂] _s	3.125	5
B	[(0/90) ₂] _s	5	3.125
D	[(0/90) ₂] _s	5	5
E	(0/+45/-45/90) _s	5	5
F	(0/+45/-45/90) _s	8	5

Table 2. Lay up and geometry of the different types of specimen under test.

TYPE	WITHOUT CONSTRAINT		SEMI-RIGID CONSTRAINT	
	LOAD KN	MODE	LOAD KN	MODE
A	2.65	D/B	4.05	T
B	2.85	D/B	5.16	B
C	3.55	D/B	5.44	B
D	3.25	D/B	5.05	B
E	1.66	D/B	3.26	B
F	1.5	D/B	3.0	B

Table 3. Failure load and mode in presence or not of a lateral constraint. (D=Delamination mode, B=Bearing mode, T=tension mode).

Fig. 3. Typical load extension plots for different applied lateral constraint :
 3.a) no lateral constraint, 3.b) semi-rigid lateral constraint, 3.c) rigid lateral constraint.

Fig.4.a Geometry of the structure.

Fig.4.b Mesh.

Fig.5 In-plane stress σ_y along the direction of the applied traction.

Fig.6 In-plane stress σ_y along the direction normal to the applied traction.

Fig.7 Normal stress σ_z around the hole. (specimen A)

Fig.8 Normal stress σ_z around the hole. (specimen E)